

Synthesis of bivalent mercury, lead, tin and zinc metal complexes with *N,N'*-bis(morpholinobenzyl)urea : a photoelectron spectroscopic study

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Hg^{II} , Pb^{II} , Sn^{II} and Zn^{II} metal complexes of *N,N'*-bis(morpholinobenzyl)urea have been synthesized and characterized.

In continuation of our study¹, we report herein the synthesis and characterization of Pb^{II} , Hg^{II} , Zn^{II} and Sn^{II} complexes of *N,N'*-bis(morpholinobenzyl)urea.

Results and discussion

All the complexes showed high melting points. The low molar conductance of the complexes ($<60 \Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) indicate that they are non-electrolyte². The ligand exhibited IR bands at 3338 (NH), 1627 (C=O) and 1110cm^{-1} (C-N-C). In all the complexes, the ν_{NH} and $\nu_{\text{C-N-C}}$ bands displayed substantial negative shift with low intensity, indicating coordination through the nitrogen of the urea moiety and nitrogen of the two morpholine entities. IR spectra of all the complexes showed no change in the positions of the $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C-O-C}}$ bands, suggesting non-involvement of carbonyl oxygen and ring oxygen of morpholine³. All the complexes showed bands at 1150–1210 (C-N), 405–495 (M-N) and $265\text{--}310 \text{cm}^{-1}$ (M-Cl)⁴.

The photoelectron peaks binding energies data of all metal ions M $2p_{3/2, 1/2}$, $\text{Cl}2p$ and $\text{N}1s$ for MCl_2 , $\text{MX}_2\cdot\text{L}$, $(\text{MX}_2)_2\cdot\text{L}$ and $(\text{MX}_2)_2\cdot 2\text{L}$ (where M = Zn^{II} , Sn^{II} , Hg^{II} , Pb^{II}

are listed in Table 1. It may be seen that M $2p_{3/2, 1/2}$ photoelectron peak binding energy values were observed more in metal salts than in metal complexes. Fig. 1 suggests that metal ions have more electron density in metal complexes than metal salts due to involvement of metal ion in the coordination⁵. Furthermore, $\text{N}1s$ photoelectron peaks have shown very high binding energy values in all these metal complexes (402.6–402.8 eV) than free nitrogen atom ($\sim 399 \text{eV}$), which suggests more effective positive charge on nitrogen atom in the metal complexes⁵ (Fig. 2). From these M $2p_{3/2, 1/2}$ and $\text{N}1s$ XPS data one can conclude that

Fig. 1. Sn $3p_{3/2}$ binding energy (eV) in SnCl_2 , $\text{SnCl}_2\cdot\text{L}$, $(\text{SnCl}_2)_2\cdot\text{L}$, $(\text{SnCl}_2)_2\cdot 2\text{L}$ complexes.

Fig. 2. $\text{N}1s$ binding energy (eV) in ligand, $\text{SnCl}_2\cdot\text{L}$, $(\text{SnCl}_2)_2\cdot\text{L}$, $(\text{SnCl}_2)_2\cdot 2\text{L}$ complexes.

nitrogen in these metal complexes are coordinated to metal ions⁵. The $\text{Cl}2p$ photoelectron spectra of all the complexes have shown more BE values in the range 201.2–201.4 eV than the starting material, which suggests that in all the metal complexes chloride ion is coordinated in the inner coordination sphere of the metal ion⁶. The $\text{O}1s$

photoelectron peak binding energy (eV) was observed in each of the metal complexes the same as in the ligand, suggesting noninvolvement of oxygen atom in bonding with metal ion (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. O1s binding energy (eV) in ligand, SnCl₂.L, (SnCl₂)₂.L, (SnCl₂)₂.2L complexes.

Table 1. M *np*_{3/2, 1/2}, N1s, Cl2*p* and O1s binding energies (eV) in MX₂, MX₂.L, (MX₂)₂.L and (MX₂)₂.2L complexes

Compd.	M <i>np</i> _{3/2, 1/2}	N1s	Cl2 <i>p</i>	O1s
Ligand	—	399.8	—	531
SnCl ₂	715.8	—	202	—
SnCl ₂ .L	713.8	402.6	201.4	531
(SnCl ₂) ₂ .L	713.6	402.8	201.4	531
(SnCl ₂) ₂ .2L	713.6	402.8	201.4	531
HgCl ₂	677.6	—	201.2	—
HgCl ₂ .L	675.2	402.8	201.2	531
(HgCl ₂) ₂ .L	675.2	402.8	201.2	531
(HgCl ₂) ₂ .2L	675.2	402.8	201.2	531
PbCl ₂	764.8	—	201.4	—
PbCl ₂ .L	762.0	402.6	201.4	531
(PbCl ₂) ₂ .L	762.0	402.6	201.4	531
(PbCl ₂) ₂ .2L	762.0	402.6	201.4	531
ZnCl ₂	87.8	—	201.2	—
ZnCl ₂ .L	85.2	402.8	201.2	531
(ZnCl ₂) ₂ .L	85.2	402.8	201.2	531
(ZnCl ₂) ₂ .2L	85.2	402.8	201.2	531

Experimental

The metal salts HgCl₂, PbCl₂, ZnCl₂, SnCl₂ were commercially available pure samples. Urea, morpholine and benzaldehyde were used after purification.

N,N'-bis(morpholinobenzyl)urea¹: To urea (1 mmol) dissolved in distilled water (10 ml) was added morpholine (2 mmol) followed by benzaldehyde (2 mmol). The mixture was refluxed for 4 h and was allowed to stand at room temperature for 48 h. The white solid obtained after evaporation, was purified by crystallization from ethanol.

The complexes: The metal salts (1 mmol) were refluxed with the ligand (in 1 : 1, 2 : 1 and 2 : 2 ratios) for 3 h and the solid products were dried at 100°.

Elemental analyses were obtained from C.D.R.I., Lucknow. Conductivity was measured in DMSO solution at room temperature using a Digisum conductivity bridge. IR spectra (CsI) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 621 spectrophotometer. X-Ray photoelectron spectra were recorded on a VG Scientific ESCA-3 MK II electron spectrometer. The Mg K ∞ X-ray line (1253.6 eV) was used for photoexcitation. The Cu2*p*_{3/2} (BE = 932.8 \pm 0.2) and Au4*f*_{7/2} (BE = 83.8 \pm 0.1) lines were used to calibrate the instrument and Ag3*d*_{5/2} (BE = 368.2) was used for cross-checking⁴. All the spectra were recorded using the same spectrometer parameter of 50 eV pass energy and 4 mm slit width. The reduced full-width at half-maximum (FWHM) at the Au4*f*_{7/2} (BE = 83.8 eV) level under these conditions was 1.2 eV.

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